

RE-ASSESSING THE CRIME CONTROL SYSTEM OF NIGERIAN POLICE TOWARD ENSURING EQUITY AND JUSTICE

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Hereafter, referred to as NPF unless the context otherwise suggests.

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Abstract: Security is crucial to human survival, as the numerous socio-economic activities that form the foundation of human survival depend on public safety and the protection of life and property. However, it is observed that reckless disregard for human dignity by the Nigerian Police is a great challenge to indigenes and contravenes the ‘rule of law’. The inquiry in this regard is as follows: Who will investigate the crimes allegedly committed by the police themselves? Using data from primary and secondary law sources, including case law and relevant internet materials, this paper evaluated the adequacy of the Nigeria Police as an agency of crime control within the context of universal standards for the protection of indigenes in line with the Constitutional Right to Life and Human Dignity and highlighted the flaws inherent in the Nigerian law enforcement system, advocating having an efficient legal framework on policing designed to salvage the current systems.

Keywords: Nigerian Police Force; Crime Control System; Human dignity; Legal Framework.

1. Introduction

This paper investigates the crime control system of the Nigeria Police Force (NPF) in relation to the statutory and Constitutional provisions on citizens’ right to life and human dignity and highlights the shortcomings in policing and the devastating effect on security and socioeconomic development in Nigeria. Theoretically, the government has adopted various frameworks for policing; however, there is no adequate provision in the Nigeria Constitution regarding citizens’ rights to human dignity and efficient crime control by the police. Nigeria has also ratified various international instruments on human rights, including the Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment; the International Convention for the Protection of Persons from Enforced Disappearances; and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR). Article 6 of the ICCPR guarantees that the right to life is the supreme right from which no derogation is permitted. Over the years, the government set up various committees to review the Nigeria crime control system and to propose recommendations for possible reforms; however, their recommendations were never implemented.

The paper concluded that inhuman treatment and unlawful killings of citizens constitute a violation of the right to life and human dignity. Hence, the government is expected to take adequate measures to prevent the arbitrary killing of human beings by individuals or law enforcement agents and must conduct effective and speedy

investigation in such instances. Also, the government must strategically restructure the police force to effectively realize its duties.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

Although Nigeria has adopted a series of legislative mechanisms to curb crime rates, gross disregard for human dignity, and incessant killings of human beings remain unabated and thus threaten socioeconomic development in the country. Considering the number of reported criminal cases and the conviction rates, it is evident that there is a disjuncture between the cases reported and those prosecuted.¹ For this reason, this paper evaluates the legislative framework as well as the crime control techniques applied by the police officers to establish any shortcomings that may contribute toward reckless disregard for the Constitutional Right to Life and human dignity in Nigeria, while also recommending best practices for possibly reducing crime rates and revamping citizens' right to human dignity in Nigeria.

1.3. Objective of the paper

The crime rate in Nigeria is very high, and despite legislative frameworks, it appears that there is a shortcoming in terms of the crime control system that has affected the current criminal investigation processes in Nigeria. Accordingly, this paper evaluates crime control techniques to identify their shortcomings and establishes strategic initiatives to effectively control crime.

1.4. Methodology

The research uses primary and secondary sources such as Constitutions, treaties, legislation, law reports, currently published articles, conventions, case laws, and relevant information from newspapers and internet sources to profound explanations for the set objective of this study, which involves exploratory and descriptive analysis.²

2. Legal framework

In terms of section 215 (3) -(5) of the Nigeria Constitution (1999), the primary duty of the Nigeria Police Force is the preservation of national security through the maintenance of law and order, and in terms of the Nigeria Police Force Act, 2020, the Nigeria Police Force Criminal Investigation and Intelligence Department (FCIID) is the highest investigating unit charged with the detection and investigation of crimes in Nigeria.³

3. Contemporary Issues

It has been revealed that the crime control system of Nigerian police has a gross disregard for fundamental human rights, ranging from unlawful killings to the arbitrary detention of innocent citizens.⁴ The use of firearms based on Police Force Order 237, which empowers the police to shoot at will, has resulted in a series of unlawful killings. Invariably⁵, the majority of such police officers are unpunished as such cases are rarely investigated. One such scenario is the Lekki massacre, where many peaceful EndSARS protesters were shot dead in Lekki, Lagos, on October 20, 2020.⁶

¹ Fagbemi (SAN), *Bola Ige, Assassination, Political Killings, and Nigeria's Justice System*''.

² Mohd Yunus, and Abdul Malek, '*Essentials of Research Method*', (2013) 7-8.

³ Nigeria, Police Act 2020; Guardian (The) Nigeria, "*Debate over new police Act and implications for criminal prosecution*", October 20, 2020.

⁴ "*Unlawful detention of a Monarch*" in the Guardian Newspaper 20 Further16; *Alade v. Federal Republic of Nigeria*: Open Society Foundation, 2015

⁵ Amnesty International, Civil Liberties Organization and Access to Justice, Nigeria: *Abia State police kill 16 'armed robbers'*, public statement (AFR 44/019/2006).

⁶ End Sars protests: People 'shot dead' in Lagos, Nigeria, 21 Oct. 2020.

It is contended that the use of Firearms should be regulated to comply with international standards; therefore, Police Force Order 237 must be amended.

Furthermore, enforced disappearances are prevalent in Nigeria. In most cases, suspects are arrested in police custody before being brought to court. Committee on Enforced Disappearances Issued a report in this regard.⁷ Amnesty International reiterated that many of those missing were extra judicially killed by police.⁸

Arbitrary detention, deprivation of liberty, intimidation, and torture of suspects are deeply rooted in the Nigerian criminal investigation system.⁹ There are a series of instances in which police officers tortured their victims mercilessly to death. Faiz Abdullahi, an 18-year-old vendor, died on 30th July in Kaduna State due to alleged torture while in police custody.¹⁰ Torture is the main method for investigating offenses in Nigeria, and such cases are usually prosecuted based on illegally obtained confessional statements.

In most cases, during the course of investigations, police have murdered scores of innocent Nigerians. A police officer allegedly shot dead a pregnant Lagos-based lawyer, Bolanle Raheem, as she and her husband were driving home from a church service on Christmas day, (December 25) in 2022 at Ajah on the Lekki expressway.¹¹ In one instance, some policemen on an illegal checkpoint along Okene-Abuja highway were reported to have invaded a passenger bus and had robbed the passengers of millions of Naira, setting the vehicle with the passengers ablaze; however, one of the passengers escaped and alerted other motorists, and the policemen were promptly arrested.¹² In another instance, Kelechi Isaac in Bayelsa state Nigeria alleged that police officers in Bayelsa extorted N3 million from him at gunpoint,¹³ also, Ugochukwu Chinyere was shot dead by police over N50 extortion.¹⁴ According to Tarry Odisu,¹⁵ the police have lost their dignity because of corrupt practices and their disregard for fundamental human rights. Consequently, most policemen have been murdered. Usman Ojedokun also reiterated,¹⁶

“The calculated actions of some ‘bad eggs’ within the Nigeria Police Force (NPF) occasionally result in the killing of colleagues.” In Nigeria, it is not uncommon for NPF personnel to be involved in criminal activities,

⁷ The Africa Report.com, Searching for loved ones: Enforced disappearances evoke fear in Nigeria. www.theafricareport.com, July 4, 2024.

⁸ Amnesty International, Killing at Will: Extra-Judicial Executions and other Unlawful Killings by the Police in Nigeria “Crime Control Policy of Nigerian Police: A Critique”: International Journal of African and Asian Studies - An Open Access International Journal, December 2009 Index: AFR 44/038/2009.

⁹ Policy and Legal Advocacy Centre, placing.org, 24 August 2022.

¹⁰ Daily Trust, ‘IGP, probe Faiz Abdullahi’s death in police custody’: dailytrust.com. 8 August 2023.

¹¹ Vanguard News, “Court sentences policeman who killed Lagos lawyer: Bolanle Lawal to death”: <https://www.vanguardngr.com> 9 Oct.2023

¹² “Will Nigeria’s “Apo six” ever get justice?” BBC .News (2005): www.omicsonline.org/open-access/law-enforcement-in-nigeria-by-the-police-force-and-the-travails-of-ruleof-law-2016 .

¹³ Premium Times Nigeria, “How police operatives forced me to transfer N3 million at gunpoint”: www.premiumsng.com. Aug. 31, 2024.

¹⁴ <https://www.nairaland.com>.

¹⁵ Tarry Odisu, “Law Enforcement in Nigeria by the Police Force and the Travails of Rule of Law,” Journal of Civil and Legal Sciences (2016) Vol. 5 Issue 5: www.law-enforcement-in-nigeria-by-the-police-force-and-the-travails-of-rule-of-law. Available online: -2169-0170-1000204(1)-pdf/

¹⁶ Usman Ojedokun, “Contributing Factors to Police Homicide in Nigeria” : Police Journal Theory, Practice and Principles, Vol. 87 (2014) 41-48: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/273.86.80> .

*such as engaging in armed robbery and/or collaborating with armed robbery gangs, as well as having an alliance with terrorist organizations.”*¹⁷

Another report of the violent attitude of Nigerian police was the case of Faith Edema, who was arrested and tortured violently by some police officers on the ground that she was the last known person seen in the company of her deceased friend, and she was alleged to have poisoned the deceased. The officers applied bottles and needles to her private part and her nipples. However, it was later discovered through a postmortem examination that the deceased had died of hepatitis.¹⁸

In addition, it is revealed that several inmates at a Nigerian female prison have suffered sexual assault in custody.¹⁹ Another impediment to the effective control of crime in Nigeria is corruption within the police force, as well as a lack of professionalism, poor training, and indiscipline.²⁰ Corruption in the NPF is rampant. Suspects must pay to be released from custody, and detainees must bribe the police to improve the conditions of their detention.²¹ According to Amnesty International,²² the Nigeria Police are responsible for hundreds of extrajudicial killings in Nigeria, and most of these cases are neither investigated nor prosecuted. Where investigation is conducted, it is at variance with international standards, and any police officer suspected thereby is promptly transferred to other states instead of being prosecuted. One such incident was the 1986 case of a Nigerian Assistant Superintendent of Police, George Iyaamu, who was sentenced by the court for aiding a Nigerian notorious armed robber, Lawrence Anini, who was alleged to have killed scores of Nigerians.²³

Adekoya reiterated the nonchalant and humiliating attitude of Nigerian police toward victims of violence as he stated that the police usually display insensitivity to victims at the police station when they lodge reports by asking them absurd questions and jesting as the victim narrates her traumatic experience, meanwhile, this attitude tends to discourage victims from reporting cases to the police.²⁴

Furthermore, inadequate resources and a lack of modern technological infrastructure have negatively impacted the crime control system in Nigeria, particularly the shoddy investigation process, which usually culminates in prosecutorial failure. For instance, in the murder case of Bola Ige (a former Attorney General of the Federation of Nigeria), the prosecution did not present any forensic evidence.²⁵ In line with this, Ladapo²⁶ conducted a survey

¹⁷ See also Editorial, *africa This Day: Police Killing of Femi Best*: allafrica.com/stories/201012230267.html. (Accessed on May 20, 2017).

¹⁸ Asagwah, Ugwu and Odom: “*A Report on the use of Torture by Nigeria Police*”: Climate of Impunity, Civil Liberties Organizations (Nigeria), 2005, 50; Felix “*Police Kill driver at checkpoint*” Online Nigeria Community Portal: news2:www.onlinenigeria.com/headline/56999-police-kill-driver-at-checkpoint.html. (Accessed on June 10, 2017)

¹⁹ Aborishade & Oni, 2020, “*Nigerian Police Officers’ Sexual and Physical Abuses Against Female Arrestees*” <https://www.researchgate.net>

²⁰ Ethelbert Lawrence, “*Nigeria and Incidences of Homicide*” *American International Journal of Social Science*, Vol. 4, No. 5, October 2015. 102-114.

²¹ NHRC, *The State of Human Rights in Nigeria*, 2007

²² “*Killing at Will*”: *Extrajudicial Executions and Other Unlawful killings by the Police in Nigeria*” Amnesty International. De.2009, Index: AFR/44/038/2009, 1 -2.

²³ “*Anini was aided by inspector George Iyamu in Areas of Intelligent Information*” www.https://ng.opera.news^tags^George-iyamu. .

²⁴ “*Using Law to serve the purpose of Women in the 20th Century*” *Akungba Law Journal* Vol. 1, No. 2, January 2008

²⁵ Fagbemi SAN, “*Bola Ige, Assassination, Political Killings And Nigeria’s Justice System*” www.gravelinternational.org/bola-ige-assassination-political-killings-nigeria-justice-system/sthash.pell2N8Qz.dpbs (Accessed on July 31,2017).

²⁶ Ladapo, “*Effective Investigations, A Pivot to Efficient Criminal Justice Administration: Challenges In Nigeria*”, *African Journal of Criminology and Justice Studies: AJCJS*, Vol.5, #s1 & 2, ISSN 1554-3897:

of prosecutors in the Oyo State Ministry of Justice (Ibadan, Nigeria) to determine the perception of the prosecutors on the quality of investigations carried out by the police, and he discovered that the outcomes of police investigations negatively affected criminal prosecutions. Ladapo further noted that the current practice in Nigeria is that police investigators take personal custody of their investigation files and when the officer is transferred to another department or other part of the country, retires, or dies. the investigation case files, which contain the statements of witnesses, statements of the accused persons, police investigation reports, and other vital documents required for criminal prosecutions, usually go missing, and consequently, suspects are arbitrarily detained in prisons indefinitely.

In a press conference in January 2005, the former Nigerian Inspector General of Police, Sunday Ehindero, stated: “The era where neophytes would be assigned to investigate criminal offenses is gone.... we are not going to put a tailor to go and investigate, we must have the census of all those people with professional knowledge, we will make use of them and nobody will be routinely posted to CID (Criminal Investigations Department) unless he has something to offer.”²⁷

However, the Nigeria crime control and investigation system has not improved. Fulani Herdsmen, Boko Haram Insurgents, and gangs of kidnapers have terrorized Nigeria for several years; consequently, these challenges have drastically affected socioeconomic development.²⁸ In an attempt to curb the incessant killing of human beings in Nigeria, the Nigeria Legislature enacted the Terrorism Prevention Act of 2011, which was later amended by the Terrorism (Prevention) (Amendment) Act of 2013. However, in November 2013, when the Nigeria Inspector General of Police was interrogated as to why the police failed to prosecute the numerous terrorists that were apprehended and detained, his response was that there was no enabling legislation in that regard.²⁹ In this regard, Sebastine said “this act of ignorance on the part of the highest-ranking Police officer depicts the insensitivity and nonchalant attitude of Nigerian Police”³⁰.

4. Conclusion

It is discovered in this study that the crime control policy of the Nigerian police is inadequate, and regular violations of the constitutional rights of indigenes regarding life and human dignity remain unabated. Thus, the paper contended that the Constitution lacks the impetus required for effective policing and crime control regulation. Consequently, a large percentage of perpetrators were undetected and unpunished.

This paper outlines and recommends a series of legal rules that must be considered by police officers in the law enforcement process. Accordingly, the Human Rights Committee and the Inter-American Commission on Human Rights have stated that the right to a fair trial before an independent, impartial, and competent court is an absolute right that cannot be the subject of exception or suspension.³¹ Hence, the law requires that all those who exercise

²⁷ This Day. Wednesday, January 19, 2005. www.odili.net/news/source/2005/jan/19/207.html (Accessed 19/01/2017)

²⁸ Ndubuisi-Okolo, and Theresa Anigbuogu, “*Insecurity in Nigeria: The Implication for Industrialization and Sustainable Development*” *International Journal of Research in Business Studies and Management*, Vol. 6, No. 5, 2019, pp. 7-16, ISSN 2394-5931 (Online).

²⁹ Sebastine “*A Critical Review of Relevant Security Laws in Nigeria Vis-à-vis Current Security Realities in the West African Sub-Region*,” Feb.2, 2015. American Society for Industrial Security Conference, 25-26 Feb.2014, Port-Harcourt: sebastinehon.com/a-critical-review-of-relevant-security-law-in-nigeria-vis-à-vis-current-security-realities-in-the-west-african-sub-region/. Accessed on August 2, 2017.

³⁰ *Ibid.* Sebastine.

³¹ Human Rights Committee, General Comment No. 32, para. 19; and *Gonzalez del Rio v Peru*, Human Rights Committee Communication 263/1987, UN Doc CCPR/C/46/D/263/1987 (1992), para. 5.2; and Inter-American Commission on Human Rights,

public power must act in accordance with the law and the Constitution; hence, police officers have a duty to society to ensure that an innocent person is not arrested or incarcerated.

4.1. Findings

In light of the aforementioned facts, it is expedient for the government to recruit competent law enforcement officers dully trained and well equipped to perform crime control duties efficiently. The most important duty of the government is to protect the lives and constitutional rights of its citizens through an effective crime deterrent policy. Every indigene deserves to be treated with human dignity regardless of their race, gender, ethnic origin, religion, or political affiliation. However, citizens must observe laws with due regard to the dignity, rights, and liberty of others.

To enhance socio-economic development in any community, the safety of indigenes and foreign investors is a paramount factor, and hence, international treaties and conventions on the rights and security of human beings across the world. Nigeria is a party to various international treaties and conventions and is thus subject to provisions and obligations.

Furthermore, the principal religions in Nigeria are Christianity and Islam. Hence, the laws in this country are founded on these religions. It is believed that Biblical and Quaranic injunctions on criminal offenses should form the basis of legislation in this country.³² In the Holy Bible and Holy Quaran,³³ God forbids unlawful killing of a human being.³⁴

4.2. Recommendations

1. To strengthen the criminal justice system and regulate the unethical practices of the police, particularly the investigating officers, it is necessary to establish efficient, independent investigative agencies. In this regard, the “Open Society Justice Initiative”: *Who Polices the Police?*³⁵ identified certain regions that had established Independent Investigative Agencies (IIA) and enjoins the regions to ensure that justice is done by empowering the IIA.³⁶ Regulations on the use of firearms should be amended in compliance with international human rights standards. Lethal force / use of firearms must only be allowed where it is required to protect life and only when

“Report on Terrorism and Human Rights”, 2002, para. 261; see also ICJ, *Trial Observation Manual for Criminal Proceedings*, Practitioners’ Guide No. 5, p. 38.

³² Suleiman Ikpechukwu Oji “*Offense of Murder: A Critical Appraisal*” *sami 2007@yahoo.com*. Justice Journal, 2nd ed. 66.

³³ Dr. Masuma Pervin, Assistant Professor, Department of Law, Northern University, Bangladesh (NUB).

³⁴ Sura Nissa, verse 92, Holy Quran translated by A. Yusuf Ali, 209, and Lixodus 30 verse 13, New World Translation of the Holy Scripture, 93.

³⁵ Open Society Justice Initiative, “Who Polices the Police?” *The Role of Independent Agencies in Criminal Investigations of State Agents*: Executive Summary and Recommendations

Open Society Foundations, Justice Initiative: New York, NY 10019, USA: www.opensocietyfoundations.org ; <https://www.justiceinitiative.org/publications/who-polices-the-police-the-role-of-independent-agencies-in-criminal-investigations> May 07, 2021

³⁶ *Ibid.* *Who Polices the Police?* identifies 11 examples from different regions and legal systems. These are: Canada, Ontario, Special Investigations Unit (SIU), Republic of Georgia, State Inspector’s Service (SIS), Republic of Ireland, Garda Síochána Ombudsman Commission (GSOC), Israel, Police Internal Investigations Department (Machash or PIID), Jamaica, Independent Commission of Investigations (INDECOM), Kenya, Independent Policing Oversight Authority (IPOA), Norway, Bureau for Investigation of Police Affairs, South Africa, Independent Police Investigative Directorate (IPID), Trinidad and Tobago, Police Complaints Authority (PCA), United Kingdom, England and Wales, Independent Office for Police Conduct (IOPC), United Kingdom, Northern Ireland and Police Ombudsman for Northern Ireland (PONI).

it is the last option. All allegations of extrajudicial executions and enforced disappearances should be investigated by an independent body.

2. The regular supply of modern technological infrastructure and adequate resources would contribute largely to the successful profiling of criminal cases in Nigeria, particularly, the establishment of a forensic laboratory in each state in Nigeria, and the improvement of working conditions and remuneration of the police to motivate them.

3. It is crucial for the police to work closely with various security groups and community leaders so that the people living within a community are sensitized toward the protection of life and identification of criminals in their domain.

4. The government should provide the NPF with adequate resources and equipment for self-protection, and every police officer must undergo ongoing training. Furthermore, it is paramount that the government rehabilitate the police through regular training on how to use CCTV surveillance systems and forensic evidence for effective investigation of criminal cases.

5. There is an urgent need to improve the collation of physical evidence on criminal matters. According to Adegbite,³⁷ the regular failures in criminal investigations in Nigeria are largely due to incompetent investigators and a lack of modern DNA-investigating facilities. It is believed that computerized record management systems should be adopted by various investigative units to efficiently maintain investigation case files.

6. Policing society cannot be effectively performed by a single agency. Accordingly, the European Asylum Support Office, 2021 (EASO)³⁸ observed that “the Nigeria Police Force is ineffective, underfunded, untrained, susceptible to endemic corruption, increasing the burden on the military to take on internal security operations.” Thus, it is expedient for the government to promote police-public cooperation, community policing, and private security outfits and embark upon effective funding for security outfits. Hence, it is important to introduce enabling laws to support and regulate the activities of various vigilante and security groups.

7. This paper proposes that various law enforcement departments should be supervised by experienced and legally trained officers who should be responsible for testifying in court regarding investigations. The German³⁹–French/Swedish systems are good examples of how the procedures can be effectively performed.⁴⁰

8. Where police officers are involved in the unlawful killing of an innocent person, it behooves the Government, where appropriate, to compensate the dependents of such victims to alleviate their sorrow. Under international law, all victims of human rights violations have the right to compensation. Article 2(3) of the ICCPR guarantees this right to victims of human rights violations, including extrajudicial execution, torture, and enforced disappearance. Victims include relatives of those who have suffered human rights violations. This right is

³⁷ Ibid. Kehinde Adegbite, “*Learning the Law in Nigeria*” 2015 Ed. 13-16.

³⁸ European Asylum Support Office, 2021 “*Nigeria Security Situation*” Country of Origin Report June 2021, p. 59. CFR, “*The Prospect of Local Policing during Security Breakdown in Nigeria*”, [Blog], July 14, 2020, <https://www.cfr.org/blog/prospect-local-policing-amid-security-breakdown-in-nigeria>.

³⁹ Julia Broder, “*How Public Prosecutors Work in Germany*”: www.deutschland.de/en/topic/politics/how-public-prosecutors-work-in-germany-text-But%20they%20mainly%20work%20 20-05-2019.

⁴⁰ “*The Public Prosecutor, its Role, Duties and Powers in the Pre-trial Stage of the Criminal Justice Process –A Comparative Study of the French and the Swedish Legal Systems*” CAIRN –INFO, *Revue Internationale De Droit Penal* 2011/3 (Vol. 82), Editor: ERES: <https://www.Cairn.Info/revue-Internationale-de-droit-penal-2011-3-page-532.htm>. Page 532-540 (Accessed on May 20, 2017).

elaborated in the UN Basic Principles and Guidelines on the Right to a Remedy and Reparation for Victims of Gross Violations of International Human Rights Law and includes the right to truth, justice, and reparation.

Most families cannot afford legal aid, whereas the Legal Aid Council offers legal aid to those who cannot afford it; however, it lacks funding and human resources; hence, many families end up withdrawing their claims.

9. Suspects should be brought promptly before court within a reasonable time.

10. Prosecution witnesses should receive adequate protection and financial support.

It is expected that the findings of this research, if dully implemented, will serve as a veritable tool in reinforcing the criminal investigative sector in Nigeria as well as aiding legislators in policy formulation toward reducing crime rates.